

Deviation in days to panicle emergence

Genetics of fertility restoration of wild abortive cytoplasmic male sterile lines in rice

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Thirteen elite rice cultivars were crossed with cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines V20 A, IR54752 A, and IR58025 A. Pusa 33, IET6148, Pankaj, Rajshree, and TCA48 were identified as effective restorers based on seed and pollen fertility of the F_1 s.

Only six testcrosses had more than 90% seed and pollen fertility in F_1 . The F_2 progeny of these were analyzed for inheritance of fertility restoration (see

table). On the basis of percent seed set, F_2 plants were grouped as fertile (above 80% seed fertility), partially fertile (20-80% fertility), and sterile (below 20% seed fertility).

Two fertility restoration genes, Rf_1 and Rf_2 , are known in rice. Two independent dominant genes govern seed fertility restoration ability of Pankaj and Rajshree; a single dominant gene governs restoration in Pusa 33.

The mode of action of the two genes varied in the four crosses. The F_2 population of V20 A/Rajshree, IR58025 A/Rajshree, and IR58025 A/Pankaj segregated into a 9-6-1 ratio, revealing epistasis with incomplete dominance. V20 A/Pankaj showed dominant epistasis (12:3:1). V20 A/Pusa 33 and IR58025 A/Pusa 33 showed monogenic segregation (see table).

Segregation for fertility restoration in F_2 populations of some crosses. Cuttack Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, India, 1991 rabi season.

Cross	F_1 seed fertility (%)	F_1 pollen fertility (%)	F_2 plants (no.)	Segregation for seed fertility ^a			Expected segregation ratio	χ^2
				F	PF	S		
V20 A/Rajshree	92	93	154	92	54	8	9:6:1	0.85
V20 A/Pusa 33	92	93	163	116	-	46	3:1	0.99
V20 A/Pankaj	90	91	130	94	26	10	12:3:1	0.67
IR58025 A/Rajshree	91	94	174	101	61	12	9:6:1	0.49
IR58025 A/Pusa 33	94	96	180	142	-	38	3:1	1.45
IR58025 A/Pankaj	92	93	121	72	39	10	9:6:1	1.91

^aF = fertile (above 80% fertility), PF = partially fertile (20-80% fertility); S = sterile (below 20% fertility).

In Pankaj and Rajshree, Rf_1 had a stronger effect on fertility restoration than did Rf_2 . Fertility restoration was high when both dominant alleles (Rf_1 , Rf_2) were present. It was less pronounced when only Rf_1 was present, and was further reduced (partial fertility) when only Rf_2 was present. The double recessive genotype ($rf_1rf_1rf_2rf_2$) did not restore fertility. Only one dominant restorer gene ($RfRf$) was found in Pusa 33.

Variation in seed fertility restoration indicates these genes have different penetrance and are affected by modifiers. ■

Restorers for cytoplasmic male sterile lines derived from MS577 A

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Several stable cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines (Pushpa A, Mangala A, ES18 A, and Intan Mutant A) developed in Karnataka carry MS577 A cytoplasm and have good agronomic traits. They could not be used directly to develop hybrids, however, because good restorers were not available. We successfully identified effective restorers for them.

We crossed the CMS lines with improved varieties and cultures and obtained 115 F_1 s at the Main Research Station, Hebbal, during 1992 dry season. Hybrids and their parents were transplanted during 1992 wet season in rows of 30 plants spaced at 15 x 20 cm. Ten plants from each hybrid were labeled. Three panicles from each plant were marked and then bagged before flowering. Spikelet fertility was calculated as percentage of filled grains.

Florets from the upper part of the panicles were collected before flowering and stained with 1% acetocarmine for pollen fertility studies. Pollens classified as fertile were fully developed, round, and stained deeply.

Individual plants were classified as fertile, partially fertile, and sterile based on pollen and spikelet fertility. Pollen

Maintainers and restorers for MS577 A CMS lines.^a Karnataka, India. 1992 wet season.

Genotype	CMS lines			
	Pushpa A	Mangala A	ES18 A	Intan Mutant A
Kumkum Kesari	PR	M	R	-
ARC11353	M	M	-	M
IPS15	PR	M	-	-
IPS16	PR	M	-	M
M102	M	M	-	-
Suweon 352	PR	-	-	PR
Basmati 370	PR	M	-	-
Netra	M	M	-	-
Nutshell	M	-	-	-
Manipur	PR	-	-	-
IET5657-33	PR	-	PR	PR
CSR107	PR	-	-	-
Mandya Vani	M	-	-	-
Mandya Vijaya	M	-	-	-
IESH1	R	-	R	-
CTH1	M	-	-	-
HWR30	R	PR	-	-
Taichung 65	M	PR	-	-
CTH 3 (Mukthi)	R	M	M	R
IET8050	M	-	-	-
IET2014	M	M	-	-
HB5	PR	-	PR	-
IET5656	M	M	M	-
HWR2	M	M	-	-
Pusa 702	-	M	-	M
Chamundi	-	M	M	-
IET7991	-	-	PR	-
M210	PR	M	PR	-
IET7191	-	-	-	-
Milyang 54	M	M	-	-
IET8050	M	M	-	-
Indrasan	-	M	-	-
Milyang 46	-	PR	-	-
Primala	-	M	-	-
Purple dwarf	-	M	-	-
IR26	-	PR	PR	-
IR36	M	-	M	-
IR42	PR	-	-	-
IR46	-	M	-	-
IR50	-	M	-	-
IR50-31	PR	M	M	-
IR52	PR	M	M	M
IR54	M	M	-	-
IR64	M	-	M	-
IR74	M	PR	-	-
IR2429-315	-	M	-	-
IR2729-105	-	M	-	-
IR2797-105	M	-	-	-
IR3429-350	PR	-	-	-
IR9761-19-1	-	M	PR	-
IR11418-15-2	-	M	PR	-
IR13146-45	PR	-	-	-
IR13249-30	M	M	M	M
IR15975	PR	-	-	-
IR18350-90	PR	M	M	-
IR21916	M	-	-	-
IR25867-29	PR	-	-	-
IR27315	M	-	-	-
IR28178-70	-	M	-	-
IR28237-31	PR	-	-	-
IR30864	-	M	M	-
IR31358-90	PR	-	-	-
IR35358-90	PR	-	-	-
IR54752-3-5-8	PR	M	-	-
V20 B	R	M	-	M

^aM = maintainer, where pollen fertility and spikelet fertility = 0%; PR = partial restorer, where pollen fertility and spikelet fertility = 1-80%; and R = restorer, where pollen fertility and spikelet fertility = 81-100%.

parents were grouped into restorers, partial restorers, and maintainers (see table).

Of the 65 genotypes tested, 5 were restorers, 28 partial restorers, and 32 maintainers. Kumkum Kesari, IESH1, HWR30, CTH3 (Mukthi), and V20 B were restorers.

A pollen parent sometimes behaved as a restorer for one CMS line and as a partial restorer or maintainer for another. This shows that marked cytoplasmic nuclear interaction exists and that expression of restorer genes varies with genetic background of the female parents. ■

Yield potential

Stability analysis of six medium-duration rice genotypes across different N levels

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We studied the adaptiveness and stability of medium-duration rice at 0, 75, 150, and 225 kg N/ha. Genotypes ADT38, CO 45, ADT90072, Vikramarya, ADT40, and ADT39 were raised in a split-plot design with four replications from Oct 1992 to Feb 1993. N levels, applied as urea in three splits, were in the main plots. The genotypes, transplanted at a spacing of 20 × 10 cm, were in the sub-plots.

Data on panicles/plant, grains/panicle, percent fertility, 100-grain weight, single-plant yield, and harvest index were collected for 10 plants per experimental unit. We used the means of those plants for stability analysis following the method of Eberhart and Russel (1966). Pooled analysis of variance showed significant differences among genotypes and N treatments for all characters. Genotype × N interaction was also significant for all characters but 100-grain weight.